

THE ROLE OF AMIR TEMUR IN THE HISTORY OF THE WORLD

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ABSTRACT

The place and significant role of Amir Temur in Uzbekistan and world history, a great general and patron of science who founded a great kingdom in his day, his long-lasting legacy as the state's ruler and champion of science, as well as the scientific studies that looked into Sahibqiran's place in global history. The evolution of science and culture during the lifetimes of Amir Temur and the Timurids, accomplished figures who worked in a variety of disciplines during this time, is discussed in this article along with their creations, moral convictions, and perspectives on education. Additionally, sources containing the guidance and teachings of our ancestor Amir Temur are mentioned.

Keywords: source, statesman, commander, science, education, justice, meeting, madrassas, mosque, culture, artist, code, history.

Introduction.

In the history of the Uzbek statehood, Amir Temur and the Timurid era hold a unique position. Following our nation's independence, unbiased opinions were voiced regarding our history, culture, notable scientists, statesmen, and commanders; scientific-practical and artistic works were produced; conferences were convened; and important details regarding the past of the time period gained fresh content and was generalized. Sahibkiran Amir Temur is an extraordinary individual who possesses great qualities as a leader, statesman, lawyer, speaker, psychologist, and supporter of

science, art, and culture. He also has a deep love for his nation and its citizens. In addition to being a current historical issue, the historiography and source studies of Amir Temur and the Timurids represent a significant historical process that has been studied during the Medieval Era. In the historiography of Uzbekistan and the world, the intriguing, fascinating, and important information in this regard is regarded as one of the hot topics that hasn't lost its significance. Science has always been interested in the study of culture as one of the main scientific facets of history. Sources related to the history of the Timurids have been translated into various languages on a global scale and scientific research has been carried out.

Amir Temur is revered as a brilliant statesman, virtuous leader, and military tactician. He dedicated his entire career to politics using humanitarian catchphrases like "Rosti Rusti," which translates to "If you are right, you will be saved," "Strength is justice". Today's generation ought to conduct a thorough scientific analysis of Temurbek's ideas and his attempts to establish state power through the use of natural intelligence, physical prowess, and military prowess. Amir Temur founded a centralized state nation with the goal of enhancing the growth and economy, bolstering cities, the resurgence of caravan routes, the growth of trade, the advancement of crafts, and agriculture laid the foundation. The advancement of science and culture was made possible by all of these. The nation's science and culture both experienced significant political and economic growth, but these factors alone were insufficient. Rich cultural heritage and a strong spiritual foundation were also necessary. Amir Temur initially focused on the cities in which he was born and raised, Shahrisabz is the capital, Aksaray is a majestic city, and stunning mosques, beautiful and opulent buildings in Samarkand. Along with Samarkand and Herat, other notable places during this time include Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz, and Balkh. Cultural hubs can be found in Shiraz, including several global scientific hubs. Hundreds of manuscripts with decorations were created by Jahangir Bukhari and other artists, who also created the magnificent architectural monuments, wall paintings, and miniatures that have survived to this day in Amir Temur's palace. There is evidence to support the claim that Amir Temur is the

founder of the Timurid period Renaissance. In Movarounnahr, Amir Temur upheld the customs of the past by celebrating each of his victories with a holiday and a marriage. Give each and every valued guest a feast. Family rituals are also performed by singers, musicians, and dancers; they typically feature big ensembles of participants like Historical sources indicate that a great number of people celebrated holidays during his time.

Literature review and methodology.

Based on scientific sources, historical data regarding Amir Temur's early years is examined using techniques like observation, analysis, and description, as well as analytical-statistical and comparative analysis and retrospective analysis.

In addition to being rooted in the XIV–XVI centuries, the events and lessons recorded in the charters of our ancestor Amir Temur hold particular importance for the development of traits like bravery, justice, nobility, patriotism, and genuine humanity—qualities that will benefit present and future generations alike. Amir Temur embodies the most developed spirituality of that era. Analyzing Amir Temur's character from the sources, he concluded, "He was a knowledgeable man who understood the background of his ancestors, was able to draw conclusions from their failures and successes, and was able to put into practice every knowledge he acquired." He was a ruler who developed strong morals and ethics, battled for justice, had a strong faith, and never got tired of learning throughout his life. He was well-versed in both secular and religious sciences, and scholars presided over his assembly.

Given the significant contributions made to modern science by well-known individuals who grew up during the Temurid and Amir Temur era, this time period is appropriately referred to as the "second revival" of the Middle Ages. The basis of Timurid spirituality was particularly strengthened by kings and princes like Amir Temur, Mirzo Ulugbek, Boysungur Mirzo, Hussein Boykaro, Babur Mirzo, and Temurid princesses because of their reverence for science and enlightenment, even at

the expense of numerous buildings, artistic endeavors, and administrative and financial labor executed. The European Renaissance writers were fascinated by

Amir Temur's personality and wrote about his activities in their works. Notable foreign historians such as E. Gibbon, F. Schlosser, G. Weber, Jean-Paul Roux, and others provided information about the activities of Amir Temur. Publications pertaining to the study of the period of Amir Temur in world historiography, the formation of the scientific direction "Temur studies," and the creation of the image of Amir Temur in fiction began much earlier. It would not be incorrect to say that this process started during the lifetime of Sahibqiran.

Results and discussion.

The 16th century truly witnessed the beginning of European scientists' fascination with Amir Temur's persona and actions. Diplomats' notebooks and the writings by authors who wrote about Amir Temur at the same time are valued sources of

historical information, and the body of work on Temur has never been broken. These days, studies on Amir Temur and the Timurids in 33 countries have been documented in more than 500 publications by foreign scholars. The third version

of Professor Lucien Keren's book album, "Travel to Samarkand, in the Time of Timur," was published in 2006. Professor Keren is the founder and president of the published in Paris by the association for the study of the history of Timurid art.

The writing and publication preparation of this book followed the guidelines of UNESCO's "Silk Road - Communication Path" initiative. The book, which pays homage to the character of our great grandfather, great general, and statesman Amir Temur, is evidently well-liked by readers based on its third edition. Members of the scientific community, including historians, physicians, astrologers, and diplomats Sa'diddin Taftazani and Sharif Jurjani Amir, encyclopedic scholars during the Timur period, were accompanied on trips to the owner by Shamsiddin Almaliqui and Maulana Abdullah al Keshi, astrologer Abdullah Leeson, physician Maulana Fazlullah Tabrizi, and others. Amir Temur was a history student who organized himself on a regular basis and was particularly knowledgeable about the

history of peoples. He engaged in lively discourse during scientific gatherings. According to Amir Temur's rule, science as well as a number of other fields, applied art, calligraphy, and industries like books and literature advanced as well. In light of independence, we have the chance to delve deeply into the spiritual and enlightening legacy of our flawless ancestors, who hold a special place in the global spiritual and enlightened arena. Our forefathers' legacy, for spiritual purification and a sense of national identity, Amir Temur, the great statesman, the patron of enlightenment, and his descendants in particular, are an endless source of spiritual wealth.

All peoples and their cultures are under his monarchy, and he has given attention to the advancement of art. When Amir Temur's Kitobot culture in Moravia meets the Synthesis of Achievements, it will be. Conditions for creation were established with the masters' inspiration, resulting in the publication of the best paper in the world. Amazing books were written in Central Asia, according to a manuscript.

Conclusion.

He was the creator and commander of the "Justice Squad," also referred to as "just avengers or messengers and the sword of God," who punished the haughty, conceited, and conceited in private, usually at night. Thus, in the history of Uzbek statehood, the era of Amir Temur and the Timurids holds a unique position. Science, culture, and architecture all advanced during this time due to Amir Temur's tireless efforts and strong guidance.

Among other things, this improved bravery, obedience, and respect. As a result, he practiced and worked on himself continuously to develop his positive traits to the fullest. Like a future great ruler, he recognized the importance of dedicating his entire life to himself to the liberty and contentment of his shrewd and diligent people.